

The Delta Gateway: Exploring Community Use of GPU Resources through a Science Gateway

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Abstract—What could a research team accomplish if given access to the latest GPU hardware? A molecular dynamics research team could process protein-ligand tests using 100 GPUs on Delta in about 3.6 days, a task that would take their local lab a full year using their own GPU hardware. A team exploring the wonders of cosmic rays is now part of the multi-messenger-astronomy revolution; they can crunch ever more data with the additional resources. With the newly built Delta system, the research community will utilize the latest NVIDIA and AMD GPUs to empower their scientific exploration. In parallel with the Delta system launch, the Delta team conducted 44 interviews with research code leads and science gateway community leads. The observations and requirements discovered through these conversations, such as optimizing Delta to support AI/ML applications and scheduling, guide the system’s configuration and the design of the Delta science gateway.

Index Terms—research computing, Delta, GPU, science gateway, NCSA

I. INTRODUCTION

The National Science Foundation awarded the Delta system (OAC-2005572) to the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign’s National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) in response to its proposal “Crossing the Divide Between Today’s Practice and Tomorrow’s Science.” Through this award, NCSA partnered with the San Diego Supercomputer Center’s Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI) to design a science gateway to tap into the Delta system and supply a user-focused interface for researchers and educators [1] [2]. The partnership will develop Delta’s science gateway and ensure Delta integrates with and supports as many extant science gateways as is feasible. Leaders from SGCI advise and guide the Delta project in achieving these usability goals. The Delta gateway project aims to help researchers find expertise to accelerate their codes for community use via science gateways. In addition, the Delta project will provide training opportunities to improve developer expertise in application development, including support for hackathons to help targeted research groups work with experts in the areas of GPU acceleration or with domain mentors.

II. UNDERSTANDING DELTA’S USER COMMUNITY

The Delta team interviewed research code leads and science gateway community leads to analyze how the research community uses GPUs and how they would like to see access to GPUs enhanced. Forty-four virtual interviews were conducted from April 2021 - June 2021, see table I.

Communities Interviewed	Contacted	Interviewed	Response Rate
Research Code Leads	35	24	68.6%
Science Gateway Community Leads	30	20	66.7%

TABLE I
DELTA INTERVIEWS

Research lead and gateway lead contact information was pulled from several sources:

- Initial contact list of researchers that have used XSEDE-allocated GPU resources, collected from XDMoD.
- Initial contact list of science gateway teams, collected from SGCI’s customer relationship management database.
- Award information, collected from funding agency websites, researcher websites, and responses in interviews.

A. Interview Design

The interviews were designed to understand the primary research goals of the projects interviewed, how their team or community utilized GPUs or would like to adopt GPUs, and what support or configuration they would need from Delta. The interviews took place through virtual hour-long calls with interviewees. Two to three Delta team members joined each interview with one primary interviewer and two supporting interviewers. Interviews were conducted from April 2021 - June 2021.

Those who had experience using GPUs were asked to share their challenges when using or accessing GPUs. Additionally, they were asked what new or existing research software codes could benefit from GPU access. Follow-on questions gathered insight on support and training expectations and barriers present in using GPUs. Those who had not used GPUs were asked their concerns about connecting to available GPU resources and if they had any research software codes that could benefit from access to GPUs. Additional questions were asked to understand their interest in using GPUs, their support to enhance their research codes for GPU usage, and training expectations.

The final part of the interviews focused on the scientific impacts of using GPUs. This question brought the conversation back to the primary research goals driving each interviewee’s project. Asking the researcher or gateway owner to discuss the impact of available GPUs for their project gave the Delta team an understanding of what the community could scientifically achieve with access to the Delta system.

B. Interview Observations

From the 44 interviews, there were several emerging patterns [3]. Fourteen interviewees had ongoing research using, or a plan to use, GPUs for AI and ML applications. These research leads or gateway leads work on physical and life sciences data projects. GPUs enable data processing and allow model training. Several interviewees noted that datasets for AI/ML are seeing some movement to standardize tagging for data. However, with the need to develop tagging standards, there is a community need to avoid bias in the datasets and subsequent interfaces. For research teams and science gateway communities focused on ML, several ML datasets are used for benchmarking. For example, Mnist, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and celebA are well-known standard benchmark datasets. In materials science, a concerted effort is underway in the ColabFit project (<https://colabfit.org>) to collect datasets used for training data-driven interatomic potentials for molecular simulations and ML models for predicting material properties.

In accordance with the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data, ColabFit provides datasets with standardized searchable metadata, extensive analytics on their scope and quality, and a Python package, colabfit-tools, to facilitate the creation and reuse of datasets. Overall, many interviews discussing ML came to the conclusion that GPUs typically have insufficient memory for specific jobs. However, with vested interest in AI/ML from the research community and funding agencies, the hope is that hardware improvements will enable more complex AI/ML jobs in the future.

A second observation was the usage gap between research teams and gateway communities that optimized research codes to use GPUs and those that needed their codes optimized. Those who have optimized codes could occupy as many GPUs as they could access. Scaling up to consume these additional resources was easy for these teams. One risk is diminishing returns if there is a miscalculation and the code needs to be run again. A second risk is these larger jobs consume the available resources and stall the scheduled run times for smaller jobs. Yet, the scientific impact of a successful large run could, for example, enable a lab to process a visualization that they estimated would take their local lab 1.5 years to process using their own GPUs.

Transitioning into science gateway lead conversations, gateway owners want GPUs for visualization, but others had alternative uses for GPUs. The interviewees using GPUs shared that they cared about controlling the number of GPUs per research code. Since most of these communities had more than one published research code, they needed to manage the submission of jobs. Gateway owners recommended that Delta use the XSEDE, now known as ACCESS, gateway API to enable science gateways to interface with Delta [4]. The challenge is that gateways typically have only one person, usually the lead or a system administrator, managing the hosting and management of the gateway. Sometimes that is the same lead that submitted the XSEDE request for their community's allocation, and sometimes it is the lead that owns the allocation. These ownership variations have bubbled up in the past for some groups as challenges.

The most considerable challenge impacting all interviewees was optimizing research codes to utilize GPUs. Fifteen gateway leads and research code leads shared that they do not currently use GPUs nor have research codes optimized to use GPUs. When asked what would be needed for the research codes to be GPU-ready, many shared that they would need a full-stack developer or software engineer to optimize the research codes to use GPUs. Some interviewees had members of their team interested in learning about optimizing code to use GPUs. Others would need to outsource this request. The community has been offered developer expertise through programs like XSEDE and SGCI. The risk is knowing if the science and community will benefit from optimizing these research codes. Additional challenges include keeping research code up to date when the availability of the developer concludes or the award concludes, and porting the code to different GPU platforms. The lack of expertise in GPU

programming exacerbates these challenges.

Science gateways often support multiple research applications, over 500 on some gateways. With numerous research applications contributed by the community, the challenge is maintaining and optimizing the code for those applications when newer computational resources become available. For example, in the case of Delta, the issue is how to package the research codes to run on Delta or submit jobs from the gateway to use available GPUs, and to optimize the number of GPUs for a given run to get maximum benefit. Overall, optimizing research code is not an easy challenge and is selective.

Interviewees also expressed interest in lowering the barrier for codes to be run using GPUs without interacting with a terminal. The Delta team has taken this feedback and set-up a preliminary science gateway to enable easy access for community members to upload and access research codes, see Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Delta science gateway homepage

These interview discussions led to defining requirements for this Delta Science Gateway interface. Interviewees expressed interest in using a graphical user interface (GUI) for uploading and running research codes, see Figure 2. Interviewees also expected the system to support this interface. Through this delivery, users less comfortable with a command line could more easily interact with the research codes.

In one conversation, it was stated that students who often attend his workshops have no experience using Linux: “The lack of knowledge of Linux has been a challenge for students.” With codes being accessible through a web interface, students could reduce the time required to start interacting with the codes. Some interviewees still wanted access to a terminal, but mainly for experimental codes. Popular tools like Jupyter Notebooks continue to be a part of research workflows for many.

By setting up a science gateway for the Delta user community, researchers will be able to make their codes accessible to end users with no additional installation required of those users. Science gateways are a collection of codes for a specific scientific community or discipline. Unique to Delta, the Delta

The screenshot shows a web form for submitting research code to the NCSA Delta science gateway. The form is titled "TOOLS: CREATE NEW TOOL" and is part of a larger page with a navigation menu including "HOME", "MEMBERS/USERS", "TOOLS", "EXPLORE", "SUPPORT", and "ABOUT". The form itself is divided into several sections:

- About your tool:** Contains input fields for "Tool Name" (with a red asterisk), "Title" (with a red asterisk), "Version" (with a red asterisk), and "At a glance" (with a red asterisk). Each field has a small text box below it providing instructions or examples.
- How do I contribute a simulation tool?:** A section with a heading and a paragraph of text explaining the contribution process.
- What tool name should I choose?:** A section with a heading and a paragraph of text providing guidelines for naming the tool.
- Suggested Screen Size:** A section with two input fields for "W" (width) and "H" (height), with values of 780 and 600 respectively.

Fig. 2. Delta science gateway form for submitting research code. Publishing options include a basic Linux-GUI based tool, a Jupyter Notebook, or an other simulation tool.

science gateway will focus on access to GPU resources, and must support many projects across many disciplines, enabling all such projects to make research codes accessible to their respective audiences. Several science gateway platforms were brought up during these interviews to help inform the configuration of the gateway. For example, several projects requested uniquely configured virtual machines to house research codes. The ability to render visualizations in the environment and make codes available via an API would impact several projects. Having gateway support, institutional login and popular tools like Jupyter Notebooks was also a popular request. This information gathering has helped the Delta team define the gateway’s initial configuration with the opportunity to expand the gateway infrastructure to support more research use-cases.

III. CONCLUSION

What could a research team accomplish if given access to the latest GPU nodes? The answer is a lot, but much more with appropriate support. The academic computing community’s needs are continually growing, and many projects need additional support to optimize their codes. The impact of the interviews has enabled the Delta project to support a variety of disciplines and user types, and will inform its approach to system operations in the coming years. The team will continue to rely on the interview results to guide gateway development decisions, and build upon feedback from XSEDE research allocations. In the future, the goal is to continue developing the Delta science gateway based on community input and requests, and to make the community’s needs heard broadly, including through advocating for more support to adapt and maintain their research codes.

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